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To cite this article: Petr Běčák *et al* 2025 *IOP Conf. Ser.: Mater. Sci. Eng.* **1337** 012006

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POTENTIAL USE OF ALBUMIN STABILIZED GOLD NANOCCLUSERS

Mini Review

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Abstract. Much attention has been focused on the properties of metal nanoclusters due to their unique features. For instance, gold nanoclusters capped with bovine serum albumin have shown fluorescent properties and potential applications as a fluorescent and bioimaging probe as well as radiosensitizer in radiation therapy and photosensitizers for photothermal and photodynamic therapy, thus serving as an imaging and therapy agent for cancer treatment. Together with other metals used in the synthesis, the fluorescence properties of these clusters may change, or take on additional unique properties as a contrast agent probe for the magnetic resonance imaging or computed tomography. The article briefly summarizes various top-down and bottom-up synthesis strategies for fluorescent BSA-AuNCs. Furthermore, it highlights their biological applications, with particular emphasis on bioimaging, biosensing, and possible therapeutic uses. Finally, the present problems and potential prospects of fluorescent BSA-AuNCs in synthesis and biomedical research are also debated.

1. Introduction

Gold nanoclusters (AuNCs) with fluorescent properties have been studied as a promising substance in nanobiotechnology due to their smaller size, fluorescence properties, high stability, wide Stokes shift, and biocompatibility [1–3]. Particularly, bovine serum albumin (BSA)-protected AuNCs, have been widely utilized in recent years for a range of biological applications, metal ions sensor, diagnostic and therapy [4].

In comparison to gold nanoparticles (AuNPs) which size is in the range 2-100 nm and gives rise to surface plasmon resonance effect, gold nanoclusters size is further reduced to several to a hundred atoms, close to the Fermi wavelength of electrons. These AuNCs manifest interesting molecule-like properties resulting from discrete electronic transitions, which fundamentally distinguish them from conventional metallic AuNPs [4].

With the rapid advancement and widespread application of nanomaterials in various biomedical fields, ensuring their efficiency, biosafety, and biocompatibility has become essential for their successful use in biological systems. Evolving field of bioimaging employs non-invasive techniques to visualize cellular components and monitor various biochemical processes both in

in vitro and in vivo relies heavily on photoluminescent fluorophores that are highly effective, photostable, non-toxic, and biocompatible.

Thus, it leads to the development of alternatives to AuNPs, better stabilized non-cytotoxic photostable and fluorescent AuNCs. As a precursor protein bovine serum albumin (BSA), the most abundant plasma protein, has been utilized for the encapsulation of AuNCs. The BSA is a relatively large heart-shaped globular protein with molecular weight 66.5 kDa [5]. It consists of 583 amino acid residues in a single chain, 35 are cysteine of which 34 cross-linked forming seventeen desulphated bridges. Due to its vast number of various amino acids, multiple potential binding sites may be feasible for the binding of metallic ions e.g. sulfhydryl -SH, amino -NH₂ and carboxyl -COOH groups [4–6]. It was found that probable binding sites of Au and Fe ions to BSA are cysteine and lysine, respectively [7]. Also addition of metal ions may change the tertiary structure of the BSA [8]. BSA is also used because of its relatively low cost, biodegradability and non-cytotoxicity [4,9,10]. BSA-AuNCs are stable and keep luminescent properties in the wide range of pH which make them very promising agents in many features, from sensing/detection to imaging [11–13]. Among the first who reported about green synthesis of BSA-AuNCs was Xie et al, where BSA played a crucial role as a reducing and stabilizing agent as well as acting as a scaffold onto which the Au ions are bonded and entrapped, by the process similar to biomineralization behavior of organisms to inorganic ions in nature [2,4]. Thus, entrapped Au ions evince intense red fluorescence with emission peak maximum around 605-640 nm, performed good stability in different pH (3-11) and in solution with high salinity up to 1M NaCl, which was accompanied by only slight changes in fluorescence properties of BSA-AuNCs, respectively [2,14].

Furthermore, BSA-AuNCs in combination with silver or lanthanum exhibit peak position shift and an enhancement of fluorescence properties, thus enabling of detection of these ions. Also, it may serve for the detection of hazardous ions such as lead, mercury etc. which quench the fluorescence properties of BSA-AuNCs.

Nevertheless, additional atoms may not only enhance optical imaging or sensing but also serve as a probe and contrast agent for magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) and computed tomography (CT) [15,16] thus broaden the utilization of formed NCs extensively.

Biocompatibility, cost-effectiveness, eco-friendly synthetic routes and the post-synthetic surface modification capability of BSA-AuNCs have made them suitable in many biomedical applications [14,17,18]. This study briefly describes possible methods of synthesis, physicochemical properties of BSA-AuNCs and possible applications, such as bioimaging, biosensing, and therapy. Finally, it presented current perspectives.

2. Synthesis and characterisation of BSA-AuNCs, bimetallic and trimetallic NCs

There are various methods how BSA-AuNCs can be synthesized. The most abundant is the bottom-up method known as atoms-to-cluster synthetic route. The use of gold-chloride salts mixed with BSA in aqueous solution is most common in this synthesis. However, other synthesis parameters may vary in terms of pH, heating method, heating time, reached temperature, purity of BSA, concentration of gold-chloride salts, mixing method, maturation process, etc. All these variation synthesis leads to changes in the process of gold nanoclusters forming which further manifest themselves in different structure and conformation of BSA and Au clusters influencing charge, size, stability, toxicity, photoluminescent properties and other features of formed BSA-AuNCs [2,9] Value of pH is probably crucial for formation process of AuNCs and AuNPs [4,9,19].

Another possible method, how to synthesize BSA-AuNCs is top-down approach, which is a usual route to prepare nanomaterials by etching larger sizes of materials such as AuNPs in the presence

Figure 1. Schematic of the synthetic routes of BSA-AuNCs consisting of bottom-up and top-down protocols. BSA, bovine serum albumin; NCs, nanoclusters; NPs nanoparticles.

of high ratio of ligands/AuNPs to form BSA-AuNCs. External triggers such as heat, or pH are also employed. However, this approach is not preferably used because of the need for purification of BSA-AuNCs from BSA and AuNPs, what is crucial to obtain pure BSA-AuNCs. Unreacted elements in the solution may decrease the fluorescence of BSA-AuNCs and hamper the detection/sensitivity. Usually, centrifugation, dialysis, lyophilization, and coprecipitation were needed to prepare BSA-AuNCs with this method [4,17,20,21].

Therefore, it is necessary to characterize created BSA-AuNCs as profoundly as possible because each synthesis route may produce its unique BSA-AuNCs. Schematic model of synthetic routes can be seen in Figure 1.

Together with Au atoms additional atoms of lanthanum, silver may be used to bound to BSA to assemble bimetallic NCs. These bimetallic NCs have enhanced or altered fluorescence properties thus leading to improved detection of ions e.g. Hg^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , Pb^{2+} , Cd^{2+} or optical imaging [22,23]. There are different ways to form BSA-Au-AgNCs. For example, BSA-Au-AgNCs can be synthesized by either mixing as-prepared BSA-AuNCs and BSA-AgNCs at room temperature or by adding HAuCl_4 to already prepared BSA-AgNCs [24]. An aqueous solution of HAuCl_4 and AgNO_3 is stirred and then added to BSA solution followed by addition of NaOH solution [25,26]. Another method is step by step addition of each metal precursor into BSA solution [23,27]. And another option is simultaneous adding of both precursors HAuCl_4 and AgNO_3 to BSA solution after which accompanied by NaOH or ammonium hydroxide and stirring to form BSA-Au-AgNCs [11,28]. Furthermore, thermal synthesis has been developed with a difference in steps such as precursor addition/mixing time/temperature of heating etc. [11,25,27,29–31].

Furthermore, BSA-AuNCs may combine with La ions to form BSA-Au-LaNCs via microwave synthesis route consist of addition of BSA and $\text{La}(\text{NO}_3)_3$ into HAuCl_4 solution followed by addition of NaOH [22]. Also BSA-AuNCs may be bond to gadolinium or iron ions to form BSA-Au-Gd/BSA-Au-FeNCs and thus gain contrast ability for the MRI [32–34]. However, using of iron oxide or iron salts in some synthesis routes may form Fe_3O_4 , Fe_2O_3 nanoparticles or superparamagnetic iron oxides (SPIONs) [35–39]. Moreover, there is a possibility of synthesizing trimetallic NCs, which is

followed by the introduction of third ion such as erbium in one pot synthesis route of BSA-Au-AgNCs [29].

3. Applications: Interaction, detection imaging, therapy

Luminescent properties and large Stokes shift make the BSA-AuNCs worthy candidate for the fluorescence imaging either *in vitro/in vivo* of carcinoma cells. Moreover, BSA-AuNCs have shown that they could be passively accumulated in the tumors *in vivo/ex vivo*. Performed imaging studies have indeed indicated deposits of BSA-AuNCs in tumor areas through enhanced permeability and retention effect [4,13,18,40–43]. Furthermore, BSA-AuNCs may be potentially used as a contrast agent probe for the visualization of tumors by CT imaging [15,16] or for optoacoustic tomography imaging [44].

Any imaging model has its own advantages as well as limitations, therefore multimodal imaging enables us to integrate information from multiple techniques, thus allows us to gain a more accurate diagnosis especially in the early stage of disease. Besides, BSA-AuNCs in combination with iron ions may form BSA-Au-FeNCs which can be utilized as a contrast agent probe for the MRI [34]. Also, BSA-AuNCs can be modified by addition of gadolinium to form either BSA-Au-GdNCs [45] or BSA-Au-Gd nanoprobe for the MRI [45–47].

BSA-AuNCs may not only serve for imaging and diagnosis but also for therapy of carcinoma disease for example as a radiosensitizer in radiotherapy or drug carrier demonstrated by [28,48] [49,50]. Moreover, BSA-AuNCs have photosensitizing abilities therefore applicable as a photosensitizer for photodynamic therapy (PDT) or photothermal therapy (PTT) [44,51–55].

BSA-AuNCs have been widely employed due to their photoluminescence and unique physicochemical properties, as a turn-on and turn-off sensing/detecting probes for variety analytes such as toxic ions and small molecules. Compared to conventional organic fluorescent labels, BSA-AuNCs offer several notable advantages including facile synthesis, excellent sensitivity, good photostability, and water solubility. These features make them highly promising candidates for the development of efficient and reliable sensors.

Silver ions present a hazardous substance for living organisms, especially for water ecosystem even in low concentration. However, upon the introduction of Ag^+ to already formed BSA-AuNCs the BSA-AuNCs show blue shift of its emission peak from 604 nm to 567 nm with enhanced intensity (in some concentrations) as reported by [56,57]. The limit of detection (LOD) was estimated to be 10 nM. Furthermore, enhancing and tunable effect of Ag^+ on the photoluminescent abilities of BSA-AuNCs is reported in various articles [57,58].

Another use is the detection of bivalent ions. Mercury (Hg^{2+}) leakage represents a danger to the ecosystem and human beings due to its hazardous and bio-accumulative properties. Nevertheless, Hg^{2+} quenched the red emitting fluorescence of BSA-AuNCs and BSA-Au-AgNCs, thus enable to be detected with LOD as low as 0.1 nM [23,59–62] or for detection and separation with the help of graphene nanofibers for special application [63]. Another highly toxic bivalent ion is lead (Pb^{2+}) however, it can be detected by the use of BSA-AuNCs combined with lanthanum (La^{3+}) ions using the fluorescence quenching method, thus synthesized (La^{3+} ion-BSA-AuNCs) can also be used for detection of Hg^{2+} and copper (Cu^{2+}) both quench fluorescence and cadmium (Cd^{2+}) which enhance the fluorescence intensity and shift the peak position. The LOD in this method are of 0.02, 0.048, 0.19, and 4.93 μM for Hg^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , Pb^{2+} , and Cd^{2+} ions, respectively [22]. For separate detection of micro biogenic metal Cu^{2+} and highly toxic Hg^{2+} the BSA-Au-AgNCs could be applied with LOD down to 0.60 nM and 0.30 nM,

respectively [23]. Detection of Cu^{2+} ions is possible with limit of detection of copper ion as low as 0.33 nM [64] and for the lysine modified BSA-AuNCs which were used for the determination of Cu^{2+} ions with a lower detection limit of 0.8×10^{-12} mol/L [65]. Furthermore, simultaneous detection of salicylaldehyde and zinc ions (Zn^{2+}) could be accomplished by the BSA-AuNCs. The process of detection is achieved by the quenching mechanism of red fluorescence accompanied by the rise of new peak in position 500 nm and 446 nm, respectively [66].

In addition BSA-AuNCs may be used for detection of anions such as cyanide CN^- , sulfide S^{2-} , nitrate NO_2^- separately, by quenching of BSA-AuNCs fluorescence with LOD being 0.2 μM , 0.029 μM , and 1.0 nM, respectively [67–69]. Interestingly, sulfide ions can be detected by BSA-Au-Ag-ErNCs, this complex has distinct and well-resolved dual emission bands at 400 nm corresponding to the emission of the BSA-Er complex and 585 nm attributed to the emission of Au/Ag-NCs under a single wavelength excitation at 340 nm, respectively. With the addition of sulfide ions, the emission intensity at 400 nm increases, while the emission intensity at 585 nm decreases, with a lower detection limit of 6.0 nM and excellent anti-interference performance [29].

Furthermore, pyrophosphate could be detected by BSA-Au-Cu complex when addition of pyrophosphate chelates the Cu^{2+} ions and restore the luminescent properties of BSA-AuNCs with wide linear range of detection (0.16–78.1 μM) and a high sensitivity (LOD is 0.083 μM) [70].

BSA-AuNCs can be fabricated for the fluorescence turn on detection of dopamine by employment of Cu^{2+} ions. The fluorescence of BSA-AuNCs was tentatively quenched due to encapsulation of Cu^{2+} ions, then restored by introduction of dopamine because of the binding between Cu^{2+} and the amino group of dopamine with LOD being 0.01 μM [71].

Furthermore, modified BSA-AuNCs can be used for sensing of acetylcholine by conjugation of enzyme acetylcholinesterase to BSA-AuNCs, the acetylcholine is hydrolyzed to choline which then quenches the fluorescence of BSA-AuNCs. This probe can be easily coated on paper and an efficient and cheap sensor can be developed and detection limit for acetylcholine is found to be 10 nM [72].

Folic acid also under certain conditions can quench fluorescence abilities of BSA-AuNCs and therefore be detected. The fluorescence quenching was fitted to Stern–Volmer equation with a linear response in the concentration range of 0.120 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ to 33.12 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ and the detection limit of 18.3 $\mu\text{g}/\text{L}$ [73].

Moreover BSA-AuNCs may be utilized for the detection of amino acids or proteins. Cui et al, proposed a fluorescence enhancing probe. The addition of cysteine decreased the surface defects of BSA-AuNCs, as cysteine molecules adsorb onto the nanocluster surfaces via thiol (-SH) bonding, forming BSA-AuNCs–cysteine complexes. This interaction effectively enhances the fluorescence intensity of the nanoclusters. The proposed method had a wider linear range over 2.0–800 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{L}$ with a LOD estimated to be 1.2 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{L}$ [74]. Furthermore, protein shell or capsule of BSA-AuNCs can be degraded or digest by some protein for example trypsin or protease, therefore leading to fluorescence quenching and detection of these proteins [75,76].

4. Conclusion

Fluorescent BSA-stabilized gold nanoclusters with diameters under 2 nm are gaining significant attention as advanced fluorescent nanomaterials due to their unique size-dependent properties. Their strong fluorescence, exceptional stability, excellent biocompatibility, large Stokes shift, and tunable emission characteristics make them highly versatile for a wide array of biological applications.

We briefly characterized the synthesis approaches, and potential biological applications in bioimaging, biosensing and therapy of carcinoma disease.

Gold nanoclusters capped with BSA have proven to be a good tool for sensing various cations and anions including ecologically hazardous ones, moreover BSA-AuNCs can be utilized for the detection of some small molecules e.g. dopamine, acetylcholine and folic acid, amino acids and proteins. Furthermore, due to their virtue values and the possibility of modifying their surface with additional molecules and in combination with other metal ions, these modifications may lead to further expansion of the feasible use of BSA-AuNCs. Therefore, they could be utilized as an imaging or contrast agent probe for MRI, CT, photoacoustic tomography and as a drug carrier, also applicable for therapies such as PTT, PDT, as a radiosensitizer for radiotherapy and help to cure carcinoma disease. Thus, studying of BSA-AuNCs is of high importance.

However, there are still numerous challenges ahead, for example relatively low quantum yield of fluorescence within a wide emission band and emission peak polydispersity. Synthesis optimization is a priority for the creation monodispersed BSA-AuNCs with higher quantum yield, which would improve the sensing/detection limits for analytic and bioimaging purposes.

Furthermore, it is essential to deepen our understanding of surface-to-ligand interactions, as this knowledge can shed light on key processes occurring at the metal surface. Such insights may ultimately enhance the applicability of BSA-AuNCs as fluorescent and bioimaging nanoprobe, as well as in therapeutic contexts. We also anticipate that novel approaches and design strategies will lead to the development of advanced BSA-AuNC nanoprobe for a wide range of applications.

5. Data availability

The data presented in this study are available on Zenodo: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15753565>.

6. Acknowledgement

This paper was created as part of the project No. CZ.02.01.01/00/22_008/0004631. Materials and technologies for sustainable development within the Jan Amos Komenský Operational Program financed by the European Union and from the state budget of the Czech Republic. This research was funded by VSB-Technical University of Ostrava, grant number SGS SP2025/095.

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